

Integrated Management of Research Instrumentation, Software, and Data for Surgical Data Science and Tactile Internet for Surgery

Lize-Mari van der Linden^{1,2} <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9831-9110>

¹ Centre for the Tactile Internet with Human-in-the-Loop (CeTI), TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany

² Department of Visceral, Thoracic and Vascular Surgery, Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus, TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany

³ National Center for Tumor Diseases (NCT), NCT/UCC Dresden, a partnership between DKFZ, Faculty of Medicine and University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus, TUD Dresden University of Technology, and Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), Germany

⁴ Deutsche Telekom Chair of Communication Networks, TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany

⁵ Faculty of Psychology, Chair of Lifespan Developmental Neuroscience, TUD Dresden University of Technology, Dresden, Germany

*Correspondence: Martin Wagner, Martin.Wagner@ukdd.de

Abstract (500 words max.)

The recent rapid artificial intelligence (AI) and data science innovations are increasing the potential for transformations in healthcare. Surgical data science is becoming a particularly promising domain for improving surgical healthcare quality, including patient outcomes, clinical training, education, and workflows. To enable the development of AI tools for surgery, there is a strong need for multimodal surgical data encompassing patient-specific, video, imaging, kinematic, and contextual information collected from pre-, intra-, and post-operative sources [1]. Additionally, the tactile internet - enabling real-time, ultra-low latency interaction - offers new possibilities for medicine and surgery, while also posing similar technical challenges like large data volumes and complex metadata handling [2]. This vast amount and scope of data come with significant technical and ethical challenges to fully realize its full potential. Technical challenges include infrastructure for data acquisition, storage, access, annotation, sharing, and analytics within regulatory constraints [3]. In this study, we focused on developing solutions for

three research facets i.e. instrumentation, software, and data management (RISD-M) in our institution. Specifically, the (1) clinical video and patient data from our surgical department and (2) synchronized data from multiple novel actuators, sensors, and video streams collected during pre-clinical experimental surgeries for research on cognitive robotics and the tactile internet [4], [5]. Here, we present our collaborative and multidisciplinary approach to developing comprehensive data management solutions for these diverse and large datasets. These solutions are custom developed software platforms, with a particular focus on the storage, sharing, and curation of clinical and experimental data according to the FAIR principles. The platform's functionality includes the collection, storage, and access to raw data files and synchronized data streams, which are appropriately contextualized by comprehensive metadata. The metadata is organized in NoSQL databases, facilitating efficient and rapid data retrieval using search terms. These platforms have been instrumental in streamlining workflows for clinician scientists, medical students, computer scientists, and engineers engaged in diverse research projects of the Centre for Tactile Internet with Human-in-the-Loop (CeTI) and the University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus at the TUD Dresden University of Technology. The platform's capacity to facilitate the rapid development of AI solutions for surgery is also expected, as the data is now FAIR and ready for machine learning applications. Despite the initial success of the platforms, further challenges still need to be addressed. Subsequent work will focus on standardization efforts, expansion and merging of the platforms, and further development of ethical and legal channels for the dissemination of the data. This presentation will demonstrate the impact of robust user-oriented solutions to overcome some of the technical challenges facing the field of surgical data science and tactile internet in surgery.

Keywords: Surgical Data Science, Health Data, Tactile Internet

Resources

- RISD-M platform for tactile internet in surgery - screencast video.
Disclaimer: This video contains footage of surgical experiments involving ex vivo organs, which may be sensitive or distressing to some viewers. Viewer discretion is advised.
<https://caruscloud.uniklinikum-dresden.de/index.php/s/aAF78sfyzB88cDp>
"Video showing the user interface of the pilot RISD-M platform created for the management of data collected during surgical experiments, including some common research workflows"
- Endomersion promotional video. <https://youtu.be/EcCggyGT8fY?feature=shared>
"Video showcasing some of the research of the Centre for Tactile Internet with Human-in-the-Loop (CeTI) in surgery"

Author contributions

L.V., A.S. M.L.M., R.R., S.R., A.W., J.B., R.Y., and M.W. contributed to conceptualization, investigation, methodology, validation, visualization, and writing. M.L.M., R.R., S.R., and A.S.

contributed to the software development. L.V., A.S., and M.W. contributed to project administration. S.S., F.H.P.F., S.C.L., J.W., and M.W. contributed funding acquisition, resources, and supervision.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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References

- [1] M. Wagner *et al.*, 'The importance of machine learning in autonomous actions for surgical decision making', *Artif. Intell. Surg.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 64–79, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.20517/ais.2022.02.
- [2] S. Senk *et al.*, 'Healing Hands: The Tactile Internet in Future Tele-Healthcare', *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 4, Art. no. 4, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22041404.
- [3] L. Maier-Hein *et al.*, 'Surgical data science – from concepts toward clinical translation', *Med. Image Anal.*, vol. 76, p. 102306, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.media.2021.102306.
- [4] M. O. Ellenberg *et al.*, 'Endomersion: An Immersive Remote Guidance and Feedback System for Robot-Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery', in *2025 IEEE Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, IEEE, accepted for publication.
- [5] R. Younis *et al.*, 'A surgical activity model of laparoscopic cholecystectomy for co-operation with collaborative robots', *Surg. Endosc.*, vol. 38, no. 8, pp. 4316–4328, Aug. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s00464-024-10958-w.